

Developing Innovations To Enhance The Production And Development Of Teachers Based On The Concept Of Social Engineers Using The Community As A Base

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 10,2023</p> <p>Accepted: October 11 ,2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Social Engineer, Innovation, Student teacher</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8428551</p>	<p><i>The research subject “developing innovations to enhance the production and development of teachers based on the concept of social engineers using the community as a base” has developed innovation “Teacher production and development based on the community-based social engineer concept” of Chiang Mai Rajabhat University and evaluate the efficiency of the innovation according to the 80/80 level criteria. The results of the synthesis of innovation lessons are in the form of "CPRD", a process in which students and teachers use soft skills to create innovations to help solve community problems and strengthen communities with a 4-step innovation system, which are: (1) C = Cooperate: Student teachers can cooperate with groups and communities. (2) P = Plan: Student-teachers can plan and work together towards goals through positive communication. (3) R = Responsibility:eachstudents are responsible for their roles and (4) D = Develop: Student teachers can bring their findings from the development to the public, which innovation in such form can raise the level of production and develop teachers and used as a method for expanding and transferring the innovation model of teacher production and development based on the community-based social engineer concept to the Rajabhat University groups.</i></p>

Introduction

From the trend of education reform in many countries, the importance of "skills" or expertise in practice, which United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) suggested that Learners should have skills that cover 3 groups: basic skills (skills necessary for life), skills for work. (basic skills for working in every profession) and specific skills (Basic skills of interested occupations), thus becoming a new era of learning skills in the 21st century.

Key skills for leaders and modern workers (Soft Skills) are Critical Thinking and Problem Solving, Creativity and Innovation, Communication Information and Media Literacy, Cross-cultural Understanding and Collaboration Teamwork and Leadership. These skills will help people to work effectively with others. and affect the success of the work as the organization hopes (NonglakIsaro, 2021) But there was a problem found “Soft Skills” are more difficult to measure. It is highly abstract because it is a skill that arises from a person's intrinsic attributes. Chiang Mai Rajabhat University Committed to producing, developing teachers and local development with the concept of Social Engineer by developing important skills of leaders and modern workers. Soft Skills it focuses on designing and testing an innovative system for organizing learning activities for Chiang Mai Rajabhat University students. to develop and evaluate performance. As well as synthesize lessons learned of innovation in enhancing production and teacher development based on the community-based concept of social engineers. To be used as a guideline for expanding results and transferring innovations as prototypes of production and teacher development to Rajabhat University groups.

Method

This research process uses participatory action research (PAR) based on the PDCA method to obtain an innovative model system to enhance teacher production and development according to the community-based social engineer concept. which has the following operating steps.

1. Development of innovation to raise the level of production and teacher development according to the concept of social engineers using the community as a base. This innovation development process uses the community as a basis, so the primary source and research documents are studied. and related theoretical concepts (Secondary Sources) operate as follows.

1.1 Use the community as a base to develop innovation to raise production and develop teachers according to the social engineer concept by organizing a forum to create research understanding by accessing the community. Build relationships with the community to study the community context, social conditions, community living and create understanding in the community. Build good relationships and create a network of community research teams.

1.2 Field visits to analyze and synthesise community data and community context. local wisdom resources and people living in the target community.

1.3 Organized a forum to create a network of researchers in the target community to participatory drive in developing innovations to raise the level of production and teacher development according to the concept of social engineers and analyzing and synthesising the needs of communities in developing innovations to solve problems and develop communities according to real conditions.

1.4 Study documents, research, concepts, theories, and synthesize the contents studied from the documents (Secondary Sources) with the primary data obtained with the community (Primary Source) to lead to the design of innovations to enhance production and develop teachers. Based on the community-based social engineer concept.

2. Evaluation of the efficiency of teacher production innovation and development based on the community-based social engineer concept. The innovation consisted of (1) a training plan for producing and developing teachers based on the community-based social engineer concept; (2) a teacher competency assessment form based on the community-based social engineer concept with the following steps:

2.1 Plan: Plan meetings with researchers and community research teams to design and create innovative production and development of teachers based on the concept of social engineers using the community as a basis. (R₁) Determine the effectiveness by appointing 3experts/experts to check the quality of the content. and performance measurement using the formula and finding the 3-level index of conformity (IOC). Then, it was used to check the quality of the content by trying out (Try out) the non-sample group. And a meeting to review research tools by experts / experts to find the efficiency (E1/E2) by implementing the plan.

2.2 Do: Develop Soft skills in a Seminar style and in a community setting PAR to develop Soft skills with workshops. (D₁) (1) Bring the innovation to trial with a sample group starting from the Pre-test Soft Skills of social engineer students. with a teacher competency scale based on the community-based social engineer concept Before implementing a training plan to produce and develop teachers based on the community-based social engineer concept. (2) Organize a workshop Guidelines for the project implementation of “Innovation development to raise production and teacher development according to the social engineer concept using community as a base” to develop the knowledge and skills of students necessary according to the social engineer concept. Project preparation, work planning, and guidelines for driving the project to achieve success.

(3) Student teachers went on an area study to study the community context and went on a community development area by organizing a participatory learning platform using the PAR model. (R₂) (3.1) Group of students, teachers, social engineers Visit the community area to study, explore, and analyze the problems/needs of the local community. (3.2) Social engineer student teachers group Arranging meetings and designing development/innovative activities that meet the needs of the local community. (3.3) Group of students, teachers, social engineers Visit the community area as a field practice in developing/transferring knowledge/applying innovation. Benefits in local communities (3.4) Take lessons/learned from work practice in participating in the project “Innovation development to enhance production and development of teachers according to the concept of social engineers using community as a basis” by students of social engineer teachers. and the local community (AAR).

2.3 Post-test Soft Skills of Social Engineer Teacher Students with a teacher competency scale based on the community-based social engineer concept.

3. The synthesis of lessons learned to be an innovative prototype of teacher production and development based on the community-based concept of social engineers. Acquired by the process of summarizing and evaluating (Check) and bringing the evaluation results to improve Return knowledge to the community (Act) with network partners There are steps to operate as follows:

3.1 Summarize and Evaluation (Check) Organize a PAR forum to reflect on (AAR) the results of community development. RLC evaluates results according to objectives and indicators and Post-test Soft Skills of students.

3.2 Summarize the results of the project and prepare a research report.

3.3 Bring research results to return knowledge to the community (Act) with network partners. community stakeholders in this step, the sustainability of the spatial problem is clearly resolved. It is an activity that occurs with a teacher who is a social engineer. Be a leader in the concept of social engineers in the local community. It originates from solving spatial problems that are integrated together based on the concept of social engineers. Between schools in the community (teachers and students), people or entrepreneurs in the community. including local government organizations as a result of solving spatial problems, people in the area

have a better quality of life. Increase income and reduce expenses (both direct and indirect) to make the community sustainable in solving problems that arise in the future.

4. Present the results of the project to the working group on social engineers of the Privy Council. to request suggestions and guidelines for extending research results to Rajabhat Universities across the country There are guidelines as follows.

4.1 Use suggestions and guidelines as a summary of project results. It is the basic information for conducting research, project evaluation, and making research reports.

4.2 Obtain a form and approach for extending research results to other Rajabhat universities.

5. Conclusion/analysis activities to prepare a complete report. Important innovations were obtained such as processes such as methods for developing local curriculum and local wisdom and/or forms and/or works such as educational games, community songs, community tourism pages. Community products, community marketing, community communication and/or methods such as formal education, informal education, informal, when using that innovation, there will be consequences resulting in sustainability in solving spatial problems clearly. This can be used to develop students and teachers to have soft skills and become social engineers. They will be social engineers who can solve problems that are consistent with the problems and needs of the community. With the continuous use of such innovations, teachers will be able to create completely social engineer students. And after graduation, he will be a local teacher who will be able to solve problems in the community and locality. Increase the value of resources, products or raw materials available locally to have more value, increase income and reduce costs for people in local communities, resulting in sustainable development of local communities.

Results and Discussion

Results of developing and evaluating the efficiency of innovation, production enhancement and teacher development based on the community-based social engineer concept It meets the 80/80 criterion, indicating that the innovation is effective.

Table 1 Results of finding the efficiency of innovation for improving teacher production and development according to the community-based social engineer concept of Chiang Mai Rajabhat University.

experimental results	number	full score	total score	average percentage
Activities organized during class (E_1)	100	60	5,000	83.33
Achievement test scores (E_2)	100	240	21,500	89.58

From Table 1, it was found that the results of finding the efficiency of innovation, production enhancement and teacher development according to the community-based social engineer concept of Chiang Mai Rajabhat University. Efficiency 83.33/89.58, meeting the specified criteria 80/80

Teacher Student Competency Assessment Results By comparing the 4soft skills before and after using the training package based on the concept of social engineers using community as a base for teacher students. Chiang Mai Rajabhat University This shows the efficiency of teacher production and development innovation based on the community-based social engineer concept. shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Comparison of teacher student competencies according to the community-based social engineer concept, 4skills before and after An experimental training package based on community-based social engineer concept for teacher students.

student skills		(μ)	(σ)	Min	Max	t-test	
						t	p-value
thinking skills	before trial	7.73	2.50	2	16	7.88**	.000
	after trial	9.66	3.05	3	17		
communication skills	before trial	80.86	10.20	42	99	8.53**	.000
	after trial	86.72	7.38	69	100		
coordination skills	before trial	48.57	6.06	32	60	12.03**	.000
	after trial	52.5	4.33	40	60		
innovation skills	before trial	48.45	6.90	27	60	11.56**	.000
	after trial	52.67	4.33	38	60		

** $P \leq .05$

The results of the synthesis of lessons learned of the innovative prototype of social engineer-based teacher production and development based on the community-based concept consisted of (1) a training plan for teacher production and development based on the community-based social engineer concept, and (2) a teacher competency scale. According to the community-based social engineer concept, a total of 8plans took 44hours, details are shown in Table 3as follows:

Table 3. Results of the synthesis of lessons learned of the innovative prototype of teacher production and development based on the community-based social engineer concept.

activities plan	plan name	duration (hours)
1	Orientation: Introducing the researcher clarify the schedule and details of the activity plan and measuring soft skills based on the concept of social engineers before joining the activity (Pre-test)	1
2	Learning about 5 social engineer conceptual tools for developing students' soft skills.	12
3	Learning opens the door to community with PBL: Project-Based Learning and CBL: Community-Based Learning.	12
4	Developing Soft Skills by learning community way of life and solving community problems with Pain point & Gain point and In-depth Interview.	6
5	Development of Soft Skills according to the learning process of PBL and CBL, along with Coaching and Mentoring.	6
6	Development of Soft Skills according to the learning process of PBL and CBL with the activity "Unboxing Innovation"	3
7	Developing Soft Skills according to the PBL and CBL learning process with "AAR" and "Lesson Summary" activities.	3
8	Orientation Activity summary and measuring soft skills based on the concept of social engineers after participating in the activity. (Post-test)	1
Note: Total time spent on learning activities according to the plan is 44 hours in total.		

From Table 3, the CPRD Model in the learning activity plan It is a learning management process that focuses on giving students or learners experiences from action through thinking, problem solving, coordinating work. with the community as a learning base the details of the procedure are as follows.

Step1) C = Cooperate: means students in the group cooperate with each other. have a good relationship There is an effort to participate in thinking and setting issues. jointly search for information that members of the group are interested in joint rational discussion Step 2) P= Plan: means collaborative planning Positive communication methods can be used as part of formulating solutions to problems. Step 3) R= Responsibility: means responsibility for roles and responsibilities in the group problem analysis resource allocation Set up a system to work together to achieve the goals that have been set. and emotional flexibility and, Step4) D = Develop: means applying the acquired findings to improve, develop, and change to reach the goals be able to present the results of concept development to the public and give opportunities for discussion and exchange of ideas.

The CPRD model is an innovation system that uses a collaborative process to plan activities responsibly to develop students' soft skills in order to develop communities with participation. Therefore, it can effectively raise the level of production and develop teachers because of 4 soft skills, namely thinking skills, communication skills. Coordination skills and innovation skills Able to develop through hands-on activities with Active Learning and community visits Community Problems Therefore, it can raise the level of production and development of teachers. As Nongluk Isaro (2021) stated that organizing activities according to the concept of social engineers Able to promote important skills of leaders and modern workers (Soft Skills) of Rajabhat University students with 4 important skills: reason-effect thinking skills see problems as challenges cognitive communication skills to solve problems Skills for working with others without conflict Mobilize forces and resources to solve problems. community innovation skills It is necessary to strengthen and develop the Soft Skills of students to be able to perform their duties according to the needs of the community. According to research findings to explore soft skills that are essential for workplaces and modern graduates in the 21st century, it was found that 8 key characteristics are as follows: 1) Work Ethics 2) Interpersonal Skills 3) Time Management 4) Problem Solving 5) Leadership 6) Teamwork 7) Communication Skills and 8) Creative Thinking) (Rattanawat Penrattanahiran and Kongsab Tongkham, 2021)

In addition, enhancing productivity and developing teachers with the aforementioned innovation package The role of instructors according to innovation in learning activities using Active Learning is consistent with Natchanan Kaewchaicharoenkit (2007) explaining that the role and participation of learners are emphasized. (Active Learning) covering a variety of learning management methods, together with a participatory learning process with the community (PAR) resulting in the creation of knowledge together It is a process that emphasizes genuine participation among stakeholders. (Stakeholders) to solve or improve the problem. It is learning that leads to permanent change (Uthaitip Jiawiwattkul, 2010) Therefore, the participation of the school community is an important and meaningful process for building relationships and working together to achieve the goals and achieve the highest results with the learners in the school.

Conclusion

Soft skills development of student teachers consists of 4 skills: thinking skills, communication skills Coordination skills and innovation skills Through action with Community Participatory Active Learning (PAR) using a progressive activity plan of the CPRD model. Therefore, it can raise the level of production and develop teachers effectively according to the following innovation systems

Recommendations

1. Suggestions from this research

1.1 People who are interested in applying the innovation before organizing development activities. Innovation should be studied first. to be able to use innovation with understanding and can develop learners appropriately

1.2 Effective use of innovation Should be familiar with the students first. will make the learners trust This results in cooperation and interest in activities.

2. Recommendations for further research

Those interested can study and research. can be extended to the policy level and developed for use in the context of educational institutions

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